

LAKBAY-DIWA ✨
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4397
p-ISSN 3082-5741

VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 1

ECHOES

of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

JANUARY 2026
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
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Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

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Volume II, Issue I (January 2026), National Circulation

ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741

Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com

Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing

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DOI 10.5281/zenodo.18503456

The Poem and the Man

I wrote a poem of love and life;
But I ended up a loveless life.
So I painted mountains, high and low;
But nobody viewed them the way I do.

I wrote a song of birds and trees,
With timeless words and melodies.
But friends and kins can't keep the tune,
They said they love to read a poem.

So once again I tried to write
A poem 'bout man, his joyful heart
Soon I discovered to my surprise
The world needs laughter and sheer delight.

I painted laughter in the man's eyes,
And made him humble, just and right,
And true enough, the world proclaims,
"If all men are the same, love reigns.